

VIBRATIONS OF A LAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAM ELASTICALLY SUPPORTED AT ONE END AND CARRYING A TIP MASS AT THE OTHER

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SUMMARY: The present work deals with the free vibration analysis of a symmetrically laminated composite beam with one end elastically supported and having a tip mass at the other free end. The governing equations for free vibrations of the composite beam are derived from Hamilton's principle accounting for the effects of shear deformation and rotatory inertia. The individual influences of ply orientation, beam end constraint, tip mass and distance between the tip mass centroid and the point of attachment on the natural frequencies of the composite beam are examined and presented in three-dimensional graphs. It is shown that the increase in the (tip mass)/(beam mass) ratio, the (radius of gyration of the tip mass)/(beam length) ratio and the (distance between the tip mass centroid and the point of attachment)/(beam length) ratio yields the decrease in the fundamental frequencies. The validity of the analysis is verified by comparison with the frequency results available in the literature.

KEYWORDS: laminated composite beam, natural frequency, beam end constraint, tip mass, ply orientation, coupling effect, timoshenko beam theory

INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of laminated composite beams as robot arms or rotating blades requires a deeper understanding of vibration characteristics of these beam structures. A beam theory based on the classical lamination theory [1] is inadequate for accurate prediction of the natural frequencies of laminated composite beams, because the effects of shear deformation are pronounced for composites due to the high ratio of extensional modulus (in-plane modulus) to transverse shear modulus. The bending-torsion coupled vibrations of generally orthotropic beams have been studied by several authors [2-5] including the effects of shear deformation and rotatory inertia. The same vibration problem of symmetrically laminated composite beams was solved by Chen and Yang [6] using finite element approach. A similar study of orthotropic beams was subsequently performed by Suresh *et al.* [7] including cross-sectional warping effects, neglecting rotatory inertia and shear deformation effects. The free bending vibrations of symmetrically laminated composite beams were discussed by Chandrashekhara *et al.* [8] and Abramovich [9]. Later on, the influence of tip mass on the natural frequencies of laminated composite beams was considered by Chandrashekhara and Bangera [10]. Recently, the free vibrations of unsymmetrically laminated composite beams were analyzed by Krishnaswamy *et al.* [11], Abramovich and Livshits [12] and Abramovich *et al.* [13].

The present paper is concerned with the free vibrations of a laminated composite beam elastically supported at one end and carrying a tip mass at the other free end as a basic model for a single-joint flexible robot arm or a rotor blade. The governing equations for free vibrations of the composite beam are derived from Hamilton's principle accounting for the effects of shear deformation and rotatory inertia. A parametric study is carried out to elucidate the individual effects of ply orientation, beam end constraint, tip mass and distance between the tip mass centroid and the point of attachment on the natural frequencies of the composite beam.

FORMULATION OF PROBLEM

Laminate Analysis

A laminated composite beam is considered, referred to a system of Cartesian co-ordinates (see Fig.1) with the origin on the midplane of the beam and the x-axis being coincident with the beam axis. The length, width and height of the beam are denoted by L , b and h , respectively. In an effort to include the coupling effects among bending stiffness, twisting stiffness and shearing stiffness of the composite beam, the linear elastic plate theory is applied in this study. Neglecting the in-plane displacements compared with the flexure-induced displacements, the displacement field for the composite beam can then be assumed as:

$$u(x,y,z,t) = z \psi(x,y,t), \quad v(x,y,z,t) = z \varphi(x,y,t), \quad w(x,y,z,t) = w^0(x,y,t) \quad (1)$$

where u , v and w are the displacement components in the x , y and z directions, respectively, w^0 is the lateral displacement of a point on the midplane, and ψ and φ are the rotations of the normals to the cross-sections. The strain-displacement relations are given by

$$\varepsilon_x = z \kappa_x, \quad \varepsilon_y = z \kappa_y, \quad \gamma_{xy} = z \kappa_{xy}, \quad \gamma_{xz} = \psi + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x}, \quad \gamma_{yz} = \varphi + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y} \quad (2)$$

The curvatures (κ_x , κ_y , κ_{xy}) can be written as

$$\kappa_x = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad \kappa_y = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y}, \quad \kappa_{xy} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \quad (3)$$

The laminate beam constitutive relations are derived based on the laminate plate theory as

$$\begin{pmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} Q_{xz} \\ Q_{yz} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{55} & A_{45} \\ A_{45} & A_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where (M_x, M_y, M_{xy}) are the moments, (Q_{xz}, Q_{yz}) are the shear force resultants, and $(\gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz})$ are the transverse shear strains. The laminate stiffness coefficients in Eqs (4) and (5) are defined by

$$D_{ij} = b \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \bar{Q}_{ij} z^2 dz \quad i, j = 1, 2 \text{ and } 6, \quad A_{ij} = b k \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \bar{Q}_{ij} dz \quad i, j = 4, 5 \quad (6,7)$$

where k is the shear correction factor dependent on the shape of the cross-section [14], and \bar{Q}_{ij} are the transformed material coefficients from the principal material coordinate system to the x - y - z coordinate system. For the laminated composite beam under study, the couples (M_y, M_{xy}) and the resultant Q_{yz} can be assumed to be zero. However, the curvatures (κ_y, κ_{xy}) and the shear strain γ_{yz} are assumed to be non-zero. Thus, Eqs (4) and (5) can be rewritten as

$$M_x = \bar{D}_{11} \kappa_x, \quad Q_{xz} = \bar{A}_{55} \gamma_{xz} \quad (8,9)$$

where

$$\bar{D}_{11} = D_{11} - \frac{D_{12}^2}{D_{22}} + \frac{(D_{12}D_{26} - D_{16}D_{22})^2}{D_{22}(D_{26}^2 - D_{22}D_{66})} \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{A}_{55} = A_{55} - \frac{A_{45}^2}{A_{44}} \quad (11)$$

Note that the D_{12} term denotes bending-bending stiffness, the D_{16} and D_{26} terms refer to bending-twisting stiffness, and the A_{45} term represents shearing-shearing stiffness of the laminated composite beam.

Governing Equations

The kinetic energy T of the laminated composite beam can be written as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \left[I_1 \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial t} \right)^2 + I_3 \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] b dx \quad (12)$$

where I_1 and I_3 are the translational and rotary inertia of the cross section of the composite beam, defined by

$$I_1 = b \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \rho dz, \quad I_3 = b \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \rho z^2 dz \quad (13)$$

and ρ being the mass density of the composite beam material. The strain energy V is given by

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \left(M_x \kappa_x + Q_{xz} \gamma_{xz} \right) b \, dx \quad (14)$$

The governing equations for free vibrations of the composite beam can be derived from Hamilton's principle, *i.e.*

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta (T - V) \, dt = 0 \quad (15)$$

where t_1 and t_2 are two arbitrary time variables and δ denotes the first variation. Substituting Eqs (12) and (14) into Eqn (15) and integrating by parts leads to

$$\bar{A}_{55} \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial x^2} \right) - I_1 \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad \bar{D}_{11} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} - \bar{A}_{55} \left(\psi + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \right) - I_3 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Solution Procedure

The harmonic solutions to Eqn (16) can be assumed in the form

$$w^0(x, t) = W(x) e^{i\omega t}, \quad \psi(x, t) = \Psi(x) e^{i\omega t} \quad (17)$$

where $W(x)$ is the lateral vibration mode, $\Psi(x)$ is the rotational vibration mode and ω is the circular frequency. Substitution of Eqs (17) into Eqs (16) yields

$$\frac{d^2 W}{d\xi^2} + p^2 s^2 W + L \frac{d\Psi}{d\xi} = 0, \quad s^2 \frac{d^2 \Psi}{d\xi^2} - (1 - p^2 r^2 s^2) \Psi - \frac{1}{L} \frac{dW}{d\xi} = 0 \quad (18)$$

where

$$p^2 = \frac{I_1 L^4 \omega^2}{\bar{D}_{11}}, \quad r^2 = \frac{I_3}{I_1 L^2}, \quad s^2 = \frac{\bar{D}_{11}}{\bar{A}_{55} L^2}, \quad \xi = \frac{x}{L} \quad (19)$$

By eliminating $W(\xi)$ and $\Psi(\xi)$, Eqs (18) can be transformed into two uncoupled differential equations as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^4 W}{d\xi^4} + p^2 (r^2 + s^2) \frac{d^2 W}{d\xi^2} - p^2 (1 - p^2 r^2 s^2) W &= 0 \\ \frac{d^4 \Psi}{d\xi^4} + p^2 (r^2 + s^2) \frac{d^2 \Psi}{d\xi^2} - p^2 (1 - p^2 r^2 s^2) \Psi &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The solutions to Eqs (20) can be expressed as

Case (I) $\left| (r^2 - s^2)^2 + \frac{4}{p^2} \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} > (r^2 + s^2)$ or $\omega^2 < \bar{A}_{55} / I_3$

$$\begin{aligned} W(\xi) &= A_1 \cosh p\alpha\xi + A_2 \sinh p\alpha\xi + A_3 \cos p\beta\xi + A_4 \sin p\beta\xi \\ \Psi(\xi) &= B_1 \sinh p\alpha\xi + B_2 \cosh p\alpha\xi + B_3 \sin p\beta\xi + B_4 \cos p\beta\xi \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\frac{\alpha}{\beta} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} - (r^2 + s^2) + \left[(r^2 - s^2)^2 + 4 / p^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ + (r^2 + s^2) + \left[(r^2 - s^2)^2 + 4 / p^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{array} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (22)$$

Case (II) $\left| (r^2 - s^2)^2 + \frac{4}{p^2} \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} < (r^2 + s^2)$ or $\omega^2 > \bar{A}_{55} / I_3$

$$\begin{aligned} W(\xi) &= A_1 \cos p\alpha' \xi + i A_2 \sin p\alpha' \xi + A_3 \cos p\beta\xi + A_4 \sin p\beta\xi \\ \Psi(\xi) &= i B_1 \sin p\alpha' \xi + B_2 \cos p\alpha' \xi + B_3 \sin p\beta\xi + B_4 \cos p\beta\xi \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $\alpha' = \alpha / i$. The constants are related by the coupled Eqs (18) as

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 &= -\frac{p}{L} \frac{(\alpha^2 + s^2)}{\alpha} A_1, & B_2 &= -\frac{p}{L} \frac{(\alpha^2 + s^2)}{\alpha} A_2 \\ B_3 &= \frac{p}{L} \frac{(\beta^2 - s^2)}{\beta} A_3, & B_4 &= -\frac{p}{L} \frac{(\beta^2 - s^2)}{\beta} A_4 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Boundary conditions and frequency equation

The associated boundary conditions for the composite beam under consideration may be written as

$$\text{at } x = 0, \quad \bar{D}_{11} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = k_r \psi \quad (25a)$$

$$\bar{A}_{55} \left(\psi + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \right) = k_t w^0 \quad (25b)$$

$$\text{at } x = L, \quad \bar{D}_{11} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = -(J + M d^2) \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} + M d \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial t^2} \quad (25c)$$

$$\bar{A}_{55} \left(\psi + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \right) = -M \frac{\partial^2 w^0}{\partial t^2} + M d \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} \quad (25d)$$

where \bar{k}_r and \bar{k}_t are the rotational and translational spring stiffnesses, respectively. J is the rotational moment of inertia of the tip mass, M is the tip mass, and d is the distance between the center of gravity of the tip mass and the point of attachment. Using Eqs (17) and the non-dimensional variable ξ , Eqs (25) may be rewritten as

$$\text{at } \xi = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \xi} = \frac{L k_r}{\bar{D}_{11}} \Psi \quad (26a)$$

$$\Psi + \frac{1}{L} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \xi} = \frac{k_t}{\bar{A}_{55}} W \quad (26b)$$

$$\text{at } \xi = 1, \quad \frac{\bar{D}_{11}}{L} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \xi} = (J + M d^2) \omega^2 \Psi - M d \omega^2 W \quad (26c)$$

$$\bar{A}_{55} \left(\Psi + \frac{1}{L} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \xi} \right) = M \omega^2 W - M d \omega^2 \Psi \quad (26d)$$

With the help of relations of integration constants in Eqs (24), inserting the solutions Eqs (21) into the boundary conditions Eqs (26) gives four homogeneous linear algebraic equations. In order that the solution other than zero exists, the coefficients A_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 4$) must be equal to zero. This leads to the determinantal equation as

$$\begin{vmatrix} k_{11} & k_{12} & k_{13} & k_{14} \\ k_{21} & k_{22} & k_{23} & k_{24} \\ k_{31} & k_{32} & k_{33} & k_{34} \\ k_{41} & k_{42} & k_{43} & k_{44} \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (27)$$

The coefficients k_{ij} in Eqn (27) are omitted because of space limitations. For a given beam, the frequency coefficients p_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) can be found by solving the frequency equation (27), and the corresponding natural frequencies ω_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) can then be calculated from Eqs (19). The roots of Eqn (27) are obtained by applying the false position method [15] with a tolerance of $\varepsilon = 10^{-8}$.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to verify the validity of the present formulation, we analyze the free vibrations of a laminated composite beam made of AS/3501-6 graphite-epoxy with the following material properties [8] :

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= 144.79 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_2 = 9.65 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{23} = 3.45 \text{ GPa} \\ G_{12} &= G_{13} = 4.14 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.3, \quad \rho = 1389.23 \text{ kg / m}^3 \end{aligned}$$

The short-thick beam ($L/h = 15$ or $r = 0.019$) is considered for the purpose of comparison with the available exact solutions. The beam width b is taken as unity for all the problems. The shear correction factor k is taken as $5/6$ for the rectangular cross-section. The frequency results are given in the non-dimensional form

$$\bar{\omega} = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho / E_1 h^2} \quad (28)$$

For computational convenience, the following non-dimensional parameters are introduced :

$$\bar{k}_r = k_r L / E_1 I, \quad \bar{k}_t = k_t L^3 / E_1, \quad \bar{M} = M / m, \quad \bar{d} = d / L, \quad \bar{R} = R / L \quad (29)$$

where I is the second moment of area of the beam cross-section, m is the mass of the beam and R is the radius of gyration, which is directly related to $J = MR^2$.

Table 1 shows the first five natural frequencies of a cross-ply laminated composite beam with different degrees of constraint at one end. It is seen that the natural frequencies of the composite beam increase with increasing \bar{k}_r and \bar{k}_t and approach those of a cantilever composite beam from Ref.[8]. Figure 3 displays the effect of ply orientation on the fundamental frequency of the composite beam with a rotational and translational constraint at one end. It is important to note that the fundamental frequency of the composite beam becomes smallest at the ply orientation $[49.4/-40.6]_s$. Although not shown here, the same

tendency is observed for the higher mode frequencies. This may be due to the fact that the shear deformation parameter s in Eqs (19) for the composite beam has a minimum at this ply orientation in the region $0^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$.

The influences of the various parameters are presented in three-dimensional graphs of the non-dimensional natural frequency. Figure 4 shows that the tip mass M reduces significantly the fundamental frequency of the composite beam more than the radius of gyration of the tip mass R . Figure 5 indicates the effects of the tip mass M and the distance d between the tip mass centroid and the point of attachment on the fundamental frequency. As with Fig.4, the tip mass M has a greater effect on the fundamental frequency than the distance d . Figure 6 represents the influences of R and d on the fundamental frequency of the composite beam with a constant tip mass at the free end. Obviously the effect of d on the fundamental frequency is higher than that of R .

CONCLUSIONS

The natural frequencies of a symmetrically laminated composite beam with one end elastically supported and carrying a tip mass at the other free end have been calculated and plotted. A parametric study was conducted to examine the individual effects of ply orientation, beam end constraint, tip mass and distance between the center of gravity of the tip mass and the point of attachment on the natural frequencies of the composite beam. The accuracy of the numerical results was confirmed by comparison with the available frequency results. The present results show that the increase in the (tip mass)/(beam mass) ratio, the (radius of gyration of the tip mass)/(beam length) ratio and the (distance between the center of gravity of the tip mass and the point of attachment)/(beam length) ratio yields the decrease in the fundamental frequencies.

REFERENCES

1. Vinson, J.R. and Sierakowski, R.L., *The Behavior of Structures Composed of Composite Materials*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1987, p.119-147.
2. Abarcar, R.B. and Cunniff, P.F., "The Vibration of Cantilever Beams of Fibre Reinforced Material", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.6, 1972, pp.504-517.
3. Teoh, L.S. and Huang, C.C., "The Vibration of Beams of Fibre Reinforced Material", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.51, No.4, 1977, pp.467-473.
4. Teh, K.K. and Huang C.C., "The Vibrations of Generally Orthotropic Beams, A Finite Element Approach", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.62, No.2, 1979, pp.195-206.
5. Teh, K.K. and Huang, C.C., "The Effects of Fibre Orientation on Free Vibrations of Composite Beams", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.69, No.2, 1980, pp.327-337.
6. Chen, A.T. and Yang, T.Y., "Static and Dynamic Formulation of a Symmetrically Laminated Beam Finite Element for a Microcomputer", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol.19, 1985, pp.459-475.

7. Suresh, J. K., Venkatesan, C. and Ramamurti, V., "Structural Dynamic Analysis of Composite Beams", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.143, No.3, 1990, pp.503-519.
8. Chandrashekhara, K., Krishnamurthy, K. and Roy, S., "Free Vibration of Composite Beams Including Rotary Inertia and Shear Deformation", *Composite Structures*, Vol.14, 1990, pp.269-279.
9. Abramovich, H., "Shear Deformation and Rotary Inertia Effects of Vibrating Composite Beams", *Composite Structures*, Vol.20, 1992, pp.165-173.
10. Chandrashekhara, K. and Bangera, K. M., "Vibration of Symmetrically Laminated Clamped-Free Beam with a Mass at the Free End", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.160, No.1, 1993, pp.93-101.
11. Krishnaswamy, K., Chandrashekhara, K. and Wu, W.Z.B., "Analytical Solutions to Vibration of Generally Layered Composite Beams", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.159, No.1, 1992, pp.85-99.
12. Abramovich, H. and Livshits, A., "Free Vibrations of Non-Symmetric Cross-Ply Laminated Composite Beams", *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, Vol.176, No.5, 1994, pp.597-612.
13. Abramovich, H., Eisenberger, M. and Shulepov, O., "Vibrations and Buckling of Cross-Ply Nonsymmetric Laminated Composite Beams", *AIAA Journal*, Vol.34, No.5, 1996, pp.1064-1069.
14. Cowper, G.R., "The Shear Coefficient in Timoshenko's Beam Theory", *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol.33, 1966, pp.335-340.
15. Conte, S.D. and de Boor, C., *Elementary Numerical Analysis: An Algorithmic Approach*, 3rd Ed., McGraw-Hill, 1981, p.72.

Fig.1. Coordinate system and dimensions of a laminated composite beam.

Fig. 2. A laminated composite beam with a rotational and translational constraint at one end and carrying a tip mass at the other free end.

Table 1. Non-dimensional natural frequencies of a cross-ply laminated composite beam with different degrees of constraint at one end ($L/h = 15$)

$(\bar{M} = \bar{d} = \bar{R} = 0)$ $[0/90/90/0]$

$\bar{k}_r = \bar{k}_t$ Mode No.	10^0	10^2	10^4	10^6	cantilever (Ref. 8)
1	0.2492	0.8800	0.9226	0.9231	0.9241
2	0.9568	3.6710	4.8739	4.8888	4.8925
3	5.9228	8.1904	11.3731	11.4345	11.4400
4	13.0597	14.8569	18.5699	18.6920	18.6972
5	20.9092	22.3594	26.0309	26.2082	26.2118

Fig.3. Effect of ply orientation on fundamental frequency of a laminated composite beam with a rotational and translational constraint at one end.

Fig.4. Non-dimensional fundamental frequency versus \bar{R} and \bar{M} for a cross-ply laminated composite beam with a rotational and translational constraint at one end.

Fig.5. Non-dimensional fundamental frequency versus \bar{d} and \bar{M} for a cross-ply laminated composite beam with a rotational and translational constraint at one end.

Fig.6. Non-dimensional fundamental frequency versus \bar{R} and \bar{d} for a cross-ply laminated composite beam with a rotational and translational constraint at one end and having a constant tip mass at the other free end.